

IN- FIELD COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE OF PADDY TRANSPLANTER AND DIRECT SEEDER OF RICE

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Abstract

Direct seeding and transplanting are the two common methods of rice cultivation. Rice is an important food crop in India and stands first in area and second in total food production. In the Vidharbha region, approximately 71.96% of the total cultivable land is under marginal-sized farms and 25.41% under medium-sized farms. In the Gadchiroli district, a wetland cultivation system is followed. The challenge of planting one seed or plant per hill in rice transplanters (RT) is still difficult to achieve due to random sowing of seeds on a nursery tray. However, due to the vigor of the seed after sowing in the field and unfavorable conditions, more seeds are still needed, and the yield is lower than that of the transplanter method. Recently, the use of direct rice seeding has increased rapidly owing to rural labor shortages and continuous increases in agricultural production costs. The study aims to evaluate the performance of mechanical paddy transplanters and direct seeders of rice for performing sowing operations more effectively and in a timely manner. The average forward speed of paddy transplanters was observed to be 2.56 km/h. The average field capacity, field efficiency, and fuel consumption of the eight-row paddy transplanter were 0.18 ha/h, 72.91%, and 6.83 L/ha, respectively, and cost of mechanical transplanting was found to be 2764 Rs/ha. In DSR, the average speed of operation was 2.89 km/h, and the effective field capacity and field efficiency was found to be 0.40 ha/h and 73.74 % with an average cost of operation of 1550 Rs/ha., respectively.

Key world – Paddy transplanters and direct seeding of rice

Introduction

India is the largest rice-growing country, whereas China is the largest rice producer. In India, it accounts for more than 40 per cent of the food grain production. Annually, rice is grown on 44.6 million ha land producing about 93.89 million tonnes. Paddy is largely grown traditionally through manual transplanting and broadcasting. The manual method of paddy transplanting gives the desired result, but it involves enormous drudgery, more human stress, and high labor requirements. It combined with labour intensive operations like nursery rising, uprooting of the seedlings, transporting and transplanting in main field requiring about 250-300 man-h/ha which is approximately 25 per cent of the total labour requirement of crop (Surendra Pal, 2018)

In broadcasting method, the seed is broadcasted by hand. This method is practiced in those areas which are comparatively dry and less fertile and do not have much labour work in the fields but very less yield. Problem for intercultural operation and in manual transplanting of paddy has a very high demand of manual labour of 360 man-h/ha. The variability of labor availability during the peak transplanting season creates uncertainty and delays in transplanting, resulting in lower yields. In addition, delayed transplanting reduces the time interval between harvesting and sowing the next crop. (Sharma et al., 2003).

Mechanical transplanting is essential for optimizing paddy transplanting timeliness and yield. Mechanical transplanting has been considered the most promising operation because it reduces the labor requirement to 50 man-hours/ha, saving time and cost of transplanting

compared to manual transplanting. It removes human drudgery and maintains row-to-row and plant-to-plant distance, which helps for easy intercultural operation in paddy fields. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate the performance of mechanical paddy transplanters. The direct seeding of paddy technique offers viable option to reduce the limitations of transplanted paddy (Gill, 2014). Dry-seeded paddy (DSR) was a common practice before green revolution in India, is becoming popular once again because of its potential to save water and labour (Gupta et al., 2006). Direct seeded paddy removes puddling, drudgery of transplanting and saving of water. The success of DSR mainly attributed to timely sowing, reduced cost of cultivation, seed rate, fertilizer, water and equal or higher yield as compared to transplanting (Mahajan et al., 2005). The comparative performance evaluation of paddy transplanters and direct seeders of rice was conducted.

Methods and Materials

Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Sonapur- Gadchiroli conducted on farm testing in 13 farmer field each year during kharif 2019-2023 to study the economic feasibility of self-propelled eight row paddy transplanter for mechanical transplanting of paddy. The commercial VST Yanji Shakti 8 Row Paddy Transplanter was selected for conducting on farm testing. It has eight row with 23.8 cm row to row spacing and 7-8 no. of seeding/ hill, from plant to plant spacing 12-14 cm. The detailed technical specifications of self-propelled eight row paddy transplanter used are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Technical Specifications of 8 row self-propelled paddy transplanter

Sr. No.	Particulars	Machine specifications
1	Make and model	VST - Yanji Shakti
2	Name	VST Agro Inputs
3	Power, KW	Power operated 2.94 KW air cooled engine
4	Type	Riding
5	Over all dimensions, (L*W*H) cm	250 x 213 x 130
6	Weight, kg	305
7	Fuel capacity of tank, liter	3.2
8	Row spacing (cm)	23.80
9	Finger type	Fixed type
10	Type of nursery	25 mm mat
11	Hill to hill distance (cm)	12-14
12	Planting Mechanism	Separate Crank Shaft & Connecting Rod System with Seedling Pusher

13	Travelling Mechanism	Single Wheel Driven
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In DSR tractor operated with 11 tyne planter was used for conducting evaluation on are detail are table 2.

Table 2. Technical Specifications of Direct seeded of rice

Sr. No.	Particulars	Specification
1	Model name	National multi crop rice grain planter
2	Brand	National
3	No. of tyne	Eleven
4	No. of rows	Eleven
5	No. of depth wheel	Two
6	Capacity with seed / fertilizer, (kg)	45 and 44
7	Ground drive wheel type	Lugged

Experimental Procedure

Field experiments were conducted to evaluate the performance of a self-propelled eight-row mechanical paddy transplanter and a direct seeder of rice under actual field conditions. Standard procedures were followed for recording operational and performance parameters. The forward speed of the tractor-operated direct seeder and the self-propelled paddy transplanter was determined by recording the time required to travel a test distance of 20 m in the field using a stopwatch. The average of three observations was considered for calculation of operating speed. During the field evaluation, key performance

parameters such as forward speed, actual field capacity, field efficiency, seed rate, fuel consumption, and cost of operation were measured for both rice establishment methods following standard testing procedures. The fuel consumption was measured using the fuel-top-up method and expressed in litres per hectare and litres per hour. For the mechanical paddy transplanter, additional observations on number of seedlings per hill, depth of transplanting, and row spacing were recorded. In the case of the direct seeder, seed placement depth and row-to-row spacing were measured at randomly selected locations in the field to assess uniformity of sowing. Show in fig 1 and 2.

1) Preparation of Mat type nursery and evaluation of paddy transplanter, 2) Field performance of direct seeders of rice and field view Results and Discussion

The operational performance of mechanical transplanting and direct seeding methods for rice establishment was assessed under field conditions. The self-propelled eight-row paddy transplanter ensured uniform seedling placement, transplanting 2–3 seedlings per hill at an average depth of 8–10 cm. The machine operated at a forward speed of 1.56 km/h, achieving an actual field capacity of 0.18 ha/h with a field efficiency of 72.91%. Transplanting one hectare required 5.36 h,

with fuel consumption of 6.83 l/ha. Mechanical transplanting significantly reduced labor requirement to 3 man-days/ha.

In direct rice seeder placed seeds at a depth of 2.5–3.2 cm with 20 cm row spacing. It operated at a higher speed of 2.89 km/h, resulting in an actual field capacity of 0.40 ha/h and a field efficiency of 73.54%. The time required for seeding was 2.5 h/ha and fuel consumption were 8.93 l/ha. The direct seeding system demonstrated improved operational efficiency and reduced input requirements.

Table 3. Field performance of eight row self-propelled paddy transplanter

Sr. No.	Parameters	T1	T2	T3	Average
Paddy transplanter					
1	Speed of operation, km/h	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.56
2	Time taken to cover 1 ha area	5.56 h	5.26 h	5.26 h	5.36

3	Depth of seedlings transplanted, cm	7	6	6	6.33
4	Theoretical field capacity, ha/h	0.23	0.24	0.24	0.24
5	Actual field capacity, ha/h	0.18	0.19	0.19	0.18
6	Seed required kg/ha	75	75	75	75
7	Field efficiency, %	71.25	73	74.50	72.91
8	Fuel consumption, l/ha	6.75	6.80	6.95	6.83
9	Yield, qtl/ha	32.40	31.5	31.7	31.87
10	Cost of operation, Rs/ha	2640	2780	2870	2764

Table 4. Field performance of direct seeders of rice

Sr. No.	Parameters	T1	T2	T3	Average
Direct seeders of rice					
1	Speed of operation, km/h	2.90	2.82	2.95	2.89
2	Time taken to cover 1 ha area, h	2.5	2.55	2.45	2.5
3	Average seed depth, cm	2.5	2.7	3.00	2.73
4	Average seed spacing, cm	20	20	20	20
5	Seed rate, kg/ha	40.50	38.00	42.30	40.27
6	Actual field capacity, ha/h	0.40	0.39	0.40	0.4
7	Field efficiency, %	72.56	76.40	71.65	73.54
8	Fuel consumption, l/hr	3.50	3.75	3.46	3.57
9	Fuel consumption, l/ha	8.75	9.56	8.48	8.93
10	Cost of economics Rs./ha	1450	1600	1600	1550
11	Yield, qtl/ha	28.40	27.5	29.15	28.35

In performance of Mechanical Paddy Transplanter

The eight-row mechanical paddy transplanter operated at an average forward speed of 1.56 km/h, resulting in an effective field capacity of 0.18 ha/h with a field efficiency of 72.91 per cent. The comparatively lower forward speed and field capacity can be attributed to the requirement of precise seedling placement under puddled field conditions, which necessitates controlled machine operation. The fuel consumption during transplanting was 6.83l/ha. The cost of mechanical transplanting was estimated at 2764 Rs/ha, primarily due to additional field operations such as nursery raising, puddling, and higher labor involvement. Despite higher operational costs, mechanical transplanting recorded a higher grain yield of 28.35 q/ha, which may be attributed to uniform plant spacing, better seedling establishment, reduced intra-plant competition, and improved root development under transplanted conditions.

In performance of Direct Seeder of Rice (DSR)

The direct paddy seeder achieved a higher average forward speed of 2.89 km/h, resulting in a significantly greater effective field capacity of 0.40 ha/h and a field efficiency of 73.74 per cent. The higher work rate observed under DSR can be attributed to the elimination of puddling and transplanting operations. However, the fuel consumption was 8.83 l/ha. The cost of operation for direct seeding was substantially lower 1550 Rs./ha compared to mechanical transplanting, highlighting its economic advantage. The grain yield under DSR was 28.35 q/ha.

Conclusions

Based on the performance conclusion, it revealed that the mechanical paddy transplanter achieved 11.04 per cent higher grain yield compared to the direct paddy seeder; however, this yield superiority was accompanied by higher cost of cultivation, increased labor input, and additional field operations such as seedling nursery raising and puddling. Conversely, the direct-seeded rice (DSR) system lower production costs, reduced labor and time requirements, and improved resource-use efficiency, particularly in terms of water conservation. Nevertheless, successful adoption of DSR necessitates precise weed management strategies to minimize yield penalties and achieve performance comparable to transplanting. In the context of escalating labor costs, time constraints, and water scarcity, DSR emerges as a technically viable and sustainable alternative for rice production systems.

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